

Solvable Quasi-Schrodinger Equation with the Hulthen Potential

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 4, 2019

In a previous note (1), we showed the Klein-Gordon equation with a scalar Hulthen potential $S \exp(-ax) / (1 - q \exp(-ax))$ could be reduced to a Schrodinger-like equation solvable by the Nikiforov-Uvarov method. In this note, we show this equation also follows from the Schrodinger equation if a lower order term is dropped. Normally, when solving the Schrodinger equation, terms are not dropped, but the Schrodinger equation is approximate when compared with a relativistic equation.. This quasi-Schrodinger equation may be solved and then one may add further relativistic corrections as discussed in (1). In this note, we solve the Schrodinger-like equation and compare the energy result to the relativistic one.

Quasi-Schrodinger Equation from the Klein-Gordon Equation

In (1), it was shown how the Klein-Gordon equation with a scalar Hulthen potential:

$$(E^2 - m^2) W(x) - 2mV(x)W(x) - V(x)V(x) W(x) = - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \quad ((1))$$

may be reduced to a quasi-Schrodinger type equation. The process involves using:

$$W(x) = \exp(-\sqrt{-E^2 + m^2} x) W_1(x) \quad ((2))$$

Then:

$$-2mV(x) W_1(x) - V(x)V(x) W_1(x) = 2 \sqrt{-E^2 + m^2} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) - \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) \quad ((3))$$

One may note $-E^2 + m^2 = -(e^2 + 2me)$. The usual nonrelativistic assumption is that $e^2 \ll 2me$. This assumption may be made here even though it turns out that $e = Am$. One then needs to ensure A is small. If this is the case, one may take leading order so m in ((3)) to obtain:

$$-2m V(x) W_1(x) = 2m \sqrt{2A}/B \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) \quad ((4))$$

((4)) is the quasi-Schrodinger equation. Here $\sqrt{2A}/B = \sqrt{2e/m}$. For the ground state, one may show that: $e = Am$ and $W = \exp(-(-EE + mm)x) W_1$ where

W_1 proportional to $(1 - q \exp(-ax))^b$. and $B=1$. Furthermore, b is 1 in such a case as shown in (1). In this note, we wish to find a general solution to the Hulthen quasi-nonrelativistic problem.

Quasi-Schrodinger Equation from the Schrodinger Equation

Equation ((4)) may also be obtained directly from the Schrodinger equation, but a term (which is of lower order) must be dropped. Normally, one does not drop terms from the Schrodinger equation. One may see, however, the exact order of m of the term being eliminated. The Schrodinger equation is an approximate equation. In general, its energy levels and wavefunction may be modified by relativistic equations. Given the high speed (maybe 10^7 m/s) of quantum bound objects (e.g. electrons or nucleons), the relativistic correction may be reasonable.

Consider the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W(x) + V(x) W(x) = e W(x) \quad ((5))$$

Let $W(x) = \exp(-\sqrt{-2me} x) W_1(x)$. Then:

$$\frac{1}{m} \sqrt{-2me} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) - \frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W_1(x) + V(x) W_1(x) = 0 \quad ((6))$$

If e is $A m$, i.e. proportional to m with A tiny, then ((6)) becomes:

$$\sqrt{-2A} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) + V(x) W_1(x) = 0 \quad ((7)) \text{ to an approximation.}$$

The term $-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W_1(x)$ has been dropped because it is of a lower order.

Consideration of a Square Well Potential as a Caution

One may at first think the above procedure should apply to all potentials. We consider here briefly the square well to show this is not the case. The use of $\exp(-\sqrt{-E+m^2}x)$ as a factor of the wavefunction removes $E-m^2$ from the LHS of the Klein-Gordon equation in all cases. This leaves: $-2m V(x) G(x) = \sqrt{-EE+mm} \frac{d}{dx} G$ as the leading m order term if e (from $E=e+m$) equals $A m$, where A is a small factor. In addition, $\frac{d}{dx} G = b V G$ ($b=\text{constant}$) which seems simple to obtain for a square well potential i.e. $G = \exp(-bVx)$. It is known, however, that energy for a square well potential is not $e=Am$, but rather $(6.28 n/L)^2 (1/2m)$. It seems the above approach has problems at the boundary where $V=0$ for the square well potential. For a square well, with an infinite potential at $x=L$, $\exp(-bVx)$, $V=\text{constant}$ cannot drop to zero. Even if there is no square well potential, there will be problems matching wavefunctions at the boundary it seems. Thus, the method used above for the Hulthen potential will not work for all potentials, even though the method seems general.

Nikiforov-Uvarov Equation

Let $W(x) = G(x)W_1(x)$ where $G(x) = (1 - q \exp(-ax))^b$ which is part of the ground state solution.

$$-VG W_1 = \sqrt{2A}/B \{ W_1 d/dx G + G d/dx W_1 \}$$

$$(1 - (B+1)) VG W_1 = \sqrt{2A} \{ W_1 d/dx G + G d/dx W_1 \} \quad ((8))$$

But $VG W_1 = \sqrt{2A}/S W_1 d/dx G$ so ((8)) becomes:

$$-(B+1) V W_1 = \sqrt{2A} d/dx W_1 \quad ((9)) \text{ Next, take } d/dx \text{ of both sides:}$$

Let $-S(B+1)/\sqrt{2A} = C_1$, $V = S \exp(-ax) / (1 - q \exp(-ax))$ then:

$$C_1 (d/dx V) W_1 + C_1 V d/dx W_1 = d/dx d/dx W_1 \quad ((10))$$

Let $z = \exp(-ax)$ so $d/dx = -az d/dz$ and $d/dx d/dx = aazz d/dz d/dz + aaz d/dz$

Then ((10)) becomes:

$$-d/dz d/dz W_1 - (d/dz W_1) \{ a(1-qz) + C_1 z \} / \{ a(1-qz)z - C_1 a \} / (aa) \{ z - 2qz^2 \} / \{ zz(1-qz)(1-qz) \} = 0 \quad ((11))$$

This is of the form of a Nikiforov-Uvarov DE for which solutions are known.

The Nikiforov-Uvarov DE form is:

$$-d/dz d/dz W_1 + d/dz W_1 [t_1(z)/s_1(z)] + W_1 [s_2(z)/(s_1(z)s_1(z))] = 0 \quad ((12))$$

Where $s_1(z)$ and $s_2(z)$ may be quadratic, but t_1 is linear.

The energy levels may be found from:

$$\lambda = -n [d/dz t_1 + 2 d/dz \phi] - n(n-1)/2 d/dz d/dz s_1 \quad ((13)) \text{ or}$$

$$\lambda = -n [(-aq + C_1) + 2 d/dz \phi] + n(n-1) aq \quad ((14))$$

λ is also given by $k + d/dz \phi$ ((15)) thus one may equate ((14)) and ((15)).

$$\phi = (d/dz s_1 - t_1)/2 \pm \sqrt{ [(d/dz s_1 - t_1)/2]^2 + k s_1 - s_2 } \text{ so}$$

$$\phi = z(-aq + C_1/2 \pm \sqrt{ z^2/4 (C_1 + aq)^2/4 + ka(1-qz)z - C_1 a(-aqz + z) }) \quad ((16))$$

The term under the sqrt must be the square of a linear polynomial so the coefficient of z , in this case, must be zero as there is no constant term. This yields: $k = C_1/q$ ((17))

$$\text{Thus: } C_1/q = -(2n+1) d/dz \phi - n(-aq + C_1) + n(n-1)aq \quad ((18)) \text{ and}$$

$$\Phi = z(-aq-C_1)/2 \pm z \sqrt{[(C_1+aq)^2/4 - C_1 a + C_q a a q]} \quad ((19))$$

For the +/- choice we take - as the plus solution leads to an infinite energy ground state. Then:

$$C_1(1/q - (n+1)) = aq (n+1)^2 \quad ((20))$$

aq is large so we drop 1/q giving: $C_1 = - aq (n+1) = S (B+1) / \sqrt{2A}$
and $\sqrt{2e} = \sqrt{2A} / B$

1/sqrt(2A) goes as sqrt(qa) so B+1 can be replaced with B as an approximation. Then:

$$\sqrt{2e} = \sqrt{2A}/B = S / [aq(n+1)] \quad \text{or:} \quad e = \frac{1}{2} S^2 S / [aq(n+1)]^2 \quad ((21))$$

This matches the relativistic term for e proportional to m exactly as is now shown.

Relativistic Energy

The relativistic result for the overall energy $E=e+m$ for the term with coefficient m is (2):

$$e+m = m \sqrt{1-4S^2S / kn^*kn} \approx m - m^2 S^2S / kn^*kn \quad ((22))$$

Where $kn = \sqrt{qqaa + 4 SS} + aq(2n+1)$ From ((22)) we see that aq must be large for $1/kn^*kn$ to be small which is necessary for $e^*e \ll 2em$. This, in turn is needed to ensure one can use a nonrelativistic scenario. For aq large,

$$kn \approx 2aq (n+1) \quad \text{so:} \quad e = -.5m S^2S / [aq(n+1)]^2 \quad ((23))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems that if one begins with a relativistic equation, one may try to reduce it using various orders of m. In particular, we consider the first power after m is removed from E (i.e. $E=e+m$) and examine the $2mV$ term after eliminating $[E^*E-m^*m]W(x)$ from the Klein-Gordon equation using $\exp(-(-EE+mm)x)$ as a factor of the wavefunction. To ensure one has the nonrelativistic scenario, we require $ee \ll 2em$. This leads to a differential equation that is not the Schrodinger equation, although it may be obtained from the Schrodinger equation as shown above. This equation may be solved exactly using the Nikiforov-Uvarov method. The energy levels (assuming aq is large which is the required assumption for the nonrelativistic case) are identical to those from a "m power" expansion of the relativistic expression for e.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relativistic Corrections to the 1D Nonrelativistic Case for the Hulthen Potential (Preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Egrifes, H and Sever R. Bound State Solutions for the Klein Gordon Equation for generalized PT Symmetry Hulthen Potential <https://arxiv.org/pdf/quant-ph/0609231.pdf>